

Evaluating the health and safety implications of cabin crew uniforms – A study of cabin crew uniforms three full-service carriers.

Anjali Dikovita

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London Metropolitan University

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1. Introduction

1.1 Business Issues

Concerns in the aviation regarding cabin crew members' physical comfort, mental health and job satisfaction are all impacted by the airline industry's emphasis on their health and safety. The primary duty of a flight attendant is to help passengers evacuate the aircraft in an emergency requiring evacuation (Waldock,1999) There may be discomfort, physical strain and long-term health problems as a result of current uniform designs that ignore ergonomic factors into account. Through bettering crew welfare, reduce absences and increasing operational efficiency, this research seeks to improve uniform design. The potential deficiencies of existing designs, which might not sufficiently take ergonomic factors into account, present a business problem.

Figure 1 Inflight Health Related Factors

1.2 Research Problem

The inadequate materials and designs of SriLankan airline cabin crew uniforms, which have an impact on the health and safety of the crew, are the research concern. A balance between design and utility cause health problems and necessitate comparative research.

1.3 Research Question

With an emphasis on fabric, fit and functionality of the airline uniform design and material affect job performance, satisfaction, health and safety. Therefore, research question for the study is,

“How do the design and material of airline cabin crew uniform impact health and safety of crew members in SriLankan airlines comparing with emirates airline and Singapore airlines?”

1.4 Research Aim

The primary aim of this research assesses the health and safety implications to make better industry standards and create guidelines for safe and comfortable uniforms in selected three airlines.

1.5 Research Objective

General Objective

- To investigate the effect of Srilankan airlines, emirates airlines and Singapore airlines, cabin crew uniforms on health and safety.

Specific Objectives

- To evaluate the three airlines' current uniform policies and procedures and the design of the uniform affect physical and psychological on cabin crew.
- Identify the three airlines respective uniform – related health and safety results
- To determine which common health and safety issues stemming from the design of the cabin crew uniforms.
- To suggest changes to the uniforms design in order to increase crew comfort and safety in the findings.

1.6 Research Rationale

In order to create safer comfortable uniform standards this fills the knowledge gap about the health effects of ergonomic uniform design by comparing cabin crew and medical specialists.

1.7 Research Limitation

Due to small sample size, self-reporting bias, lack of access to proprietary uniform data and limited generalized to airlines, the study may have certain drawbacks still, it intends to provide insightful information.

2. Literature Review

2.1 The key concepts in the design of cabin crew uniforms: Health, Safety and Comfort

The term “uniform design” describes how the components, fit and accessories of cabin crew affect work pattern and productivity. Designing jobs and work setting with the needs of the user in mind is known as ergonomics and its essential for reducing accidents and improving comfort. Workplace health and safety refers to action taken to avoid health issues and injuries associated to the workplace, particularly those brought on by uniform design.

Additional studies on the functional movements required of flight attendants as they perform their duties as well as addressing issues with sizing and thermal comfort are needed (Emerson,2023).

Studies proof that unhealthy conditions like musculoskeletal disorders, skin eczema and psychological stress can be brought on by poorly made uniforms. A slew of health issues reported by flight attendants over the past decade rashes, blisters, hair loss, vomiting, migraine and shortness of breath may have something to do with chemicals in their uniforms (Harvard,2024). Cabin crew well being and safety can be enhanced by ergonomic design, which allows for natural body movements and reduces discomfort and injuries. This emphasizes the significance of uniform design.

2.2 Theoretical Frame Work

The bowtie method assists in identifying and managing design risks. Attempts to gain insight into, and manage risk have resulted in a lot of methodologies available to systematically analyse and assess risk (Ruijter and Guldenmund, 2016). Heinrich’s accident triangle emphasizes discomfort risks. To test Heinrich’s pyramid, we correlated the estimated incidence of accidents with the estimated probabilities of minor, serious and fatal accidents at the company level (Marshall, Hirmas and singer ,2018). Herzberg’s two factor theory connects job satisfaction to uniform comfort. Herzberg used this model to explain that an individual at work can be satisfied and

dissatisfied at the same time as these two sets of factors work in separate sequences (Alrawahi et al.2020).

2.3 Identification of Research Gap

There is limited study on ergonomics and worker health in the aviation sector; most studies concentrate on broad issues like clothing and ergonomic design, ignoring the particular requirements and difficulties faced by cabin crew. this omits how many carriers have varying policies and requirements as well as how uniform elements affect cabin crew productivity.

This study's conceptual framework investigates the ways in which various aspects of cabin crew uniforms impact health and safety results.

2.4 The Outcome: Important factors consist of uniform material

The present research looks at how cabin crew attire affects results related to health and safety. Accessories, fit and design and uniform material are important factors. Comfort is defined by how easy it is to move around and how satisfied with the uniform components are used to evaluate safety. Uniform design is to use to assess job satisfaction.

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Methodology

The research concept, methodology and techniques used to examine the potential effects of cabin crew uniforms on aviation industry health and safety are described in this section will outline the stages of the research process, from philosophical perspective to data collection and analysis, using Saunders’ research onion as a guide. In addition, even when methodology of review is valid, there are often issues with what constitutes a good contribution (Snyder,2019).

3.2 Saunders’ Research Onion

The steps in the study design process are shown in Saunders’ research onion, which highlight the significance of a methodological and explicit approach. Time horizons, techniques and processes, research philosophy, research approach, research strategy and research choices are among the layers. By navigating through these layers, this study guarantees a solid and holistic research design.in the other words, the research onion guides the researcher through all the steps that need to be taken when developing a research methodology (Tengli,2020).

Figure 2 Saunders Research Onion Model

3.3 Philosophical Choice

According to pragmatism research philosophy, research question is the most important determinant of the research philosophy. Pragmatics can combine both positivist and interpretivism position within the scope of a single research according to the nature of the research question (business research methodology ,2011). In order to present a fair analysis, this research embraces a pragmatic philosophy and incorporates positivist components. Because pragmatism allows for the flexible combination of qualitative and quantitative methodologies, it is a preferred approach for conducting a through investigation of the research subject. It recognizes both the subjective experiences of cabin crew members with regard to their uniforms and the objective realities of health outcome.

3.4 Research Approach and Strategy

The study applies a mixed – methods strategy, which collects and analyzes data using both quantitative and qualitative methods. A deeper, more complex knowledge of the research problem is offered by this dual method.

3.5 Quantitative Approach

Quantitative science is about finding valid mathematical representations for empirical phenomena (Borgstede and Scholz,2024). To gather information on reported health issues, ergonomic concerns and satisfaction levels, a survey is used in quantitative component.in order to facilitate a comparative examination of health and safety outcomes associated to uniforms, this survey will be made available to a broader sample of participants, including medical specialists and cabin crew. The quantifiable statistics will offer quantifiable proof in favor of or against the conclusions drawn from the qualitative study.

3.6 Population

The population under investigation include cabin crew members from SriLankan airlines, Emirates airlines and Singapore airlines, as well as medical specialists like doctors and nurses. This varied group offers a through understanding of health and safety concerns associated to uniforms, enabling comparisons between various professions and uniform styles.

POPULATION GROUP	NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS
SriLankan Airlines Cabin Crew	20
Emirates Airlines Cabin Crew	20
Singapore Airlines Cabin Crew	20
Medical Specialists (Doctors and Nurses)	10
Total	70

Table 1 Census Plan

3.7 Sampling Frame

Cabin crew from three airlines and medical specialist make up sampling frame. The study used a purposive sample strategy to identify people who possess substantial experience wearing their particular uniforms. In order to provide a thorough viewpoint of matters pertaining to uniforms, the sample will compromise a varied range of participants with respect to age, gender and tenture. About 70 people are intended sample size for the survey, and 7 to 10 people are the intended sample size for the interviews.

GROUP	AGE RANGE	GENDER	TENTURE RANGE	NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS
SriLankan Airlines Cabin Crew	25-40	Male & Female	1-10 years	20
Emirates Airlines Cabin Crew	25-45	Male & Female	2-15 years	20
Singapore Airlines Cabin Crew	30-50	Male & Female	5-20 years	20
Medical Specialists	30-55	Male & Female	5-25 years	10
Total				70

Table 2 Sampling Frame

3.8 Qualitative Approach

Members of the Srilankan airlines, Emirates airlines and Singapore airlines participated in semi structure interviews for the study's qualitative component. A detailed description of theoretical and practical aspects of qualitative interviewing and participant observation is presented, followed by a discussion of qualitative data analysis and issues pertaining to the portability, applicability and qualitative research (Moen and Middlethon,2015). The purpose of these interviews is to learn about the participants' opinions on uniform comfort, safety and job satisfaction.

Furthermore, conducting interviews with medical specialists (such as doctors and nurses) will yield comparative perspectives on uniform related concerns pertaining to various occupations. A total of 7 interviews will be conducted estimated time duration expected time 30 to 45 minutes for each interview. In depth narrative insights into the individual experiences and viewpoints of the participants will be provided by the qualitative data.

The three airlines are the subject of a case study approach as part of the research strategy. Which offers a through analysis of uniform regulation and procedures. This method enables a comparative investigation, highlighting similarities and variations in the methods that uniform designs affect the wellbeing of crew members.

Mixed method research

Investigation of mixed method triangulation made possible by the mixed methods design, which improves the validity and dependability of the results. Thematic analysis will be used to examine the qualitative data in order to find themes and patterns in the responses of the participants. to find correlations between uniform design variables and health outcomes, statistical analysis of the quantitative data will be performed, including descriptive statics and correlation analysis.

4. Time Plan

Gantt Chart

Researcher - Anjali Dikovita

Research Title - Evaluating the health and safety implications of cabin crew uniforms – A study of cabin crew uniforms three full-service carriers

No.	Task	Duration (Weeks)	2024/2025																							
			August				September				October				November				December				January			
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
1	Approval of Research Proposal	1	█																							
2	Research Report	1		█																						
3	Literature Review	2			█	█																				
4	Methodology Planning	1					█																			
5	Respondent Recruitment	2						█	█																	
6	Questionnaire Design	1								█																
7	Questionnaire Survey	2									█	█														
8	Survey Analysis	2											█	█												
9	In-depth Interviews	3													█	█	█									
10	Content Analysis	2																█	█							
11	Data Presentation	1																			█					
12	Discussion of Data Findings	1																				█				
13	Conclusion and Recommendations	1																					█			
14	Research Report Compilations	1																						█		
15	Final Review and Submission	1																							█	

Table 3 Work Plan

5. Ethical Considerations

Appropriate ethical guidelines will be followed during the study to guarantee the reliability and security of each individual. Important ethical factors include informed consent, in which subjects will receive a thorough explanation of the goals, methods and rights of the study. to guarantee keep all personal information confidential and anonymous. To apply bias reduction techniques into practice, such as ensuring individuals are diversly represented and disclosing results in an open manner. Furthermore, ethical clearance from pertinent institutional review boards will be requested to ensure compliance with ethical research procedures.

5.1 The Conclusion and Recommendation

In conclusion, this research offers insightful information of cabin crew uniform on health and safety. Airlines need to convey ergonomic design, which includes breathable fabrics and comfortable fits, and regularly include crew feedback in uniform modification to improve crew well-being.

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